

Novel borophosphosilicate bioactive glass composition – analysis and corrosion behavior

Petr Chrást^{*1}, Martin Michálek¹, Jozef Kraxner¹ and Dušan Galusek¹

^{*}) corresponding author: petr.chrast@tuni.sk

- 1) Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin, Trencin, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the tissue engineering (TE) field requires research and production of bioactive materials, which facilitate healing processes to greater extent than bioactive materials produced in earlier stages of bioactive material research (Hench's silicate Bioglass^{1, 2})

The most important factors that the bioactive material has to introduce into the process of recovery or injury mitigation are creation of a chemical bond between the artificial tissue (bioactive material) and the original (maternal) tissue, and the subsequent tissue regeneration induced by the decomposition of bioactive material. Hence, the requirements for the bioactive material matrix are both to be durable to withstand the natural conditions of the human body and to be biologically degradable and non-toxic at the same time.

Glass as a bioactive material offers its dissolution in aqueous media as one of the more defined properties. It also can be fabricated into various shapes by melting or by melting and pulverizing, with subsequent pressing or 3D printing of the glass powder into the field of tissue engineering. The glass material alone does not achieve required performance in terms of tensile strength and other factors of mechanical resistance. It is therefore more preferably utilized in composite materials to increase its mechanical durability, since retaining the original mechanical properties of an implant is the key factor for its utilization *in vivo*.

Dissolution of glass matrix takes place through a sequence of reactions^{3, 4}. In approximation, aqueous media react with the bridging oxygen bonds while the corrosion products (ions of glass modifiers or fragments of glass network formers) are slowly released into the surrounding environment. This changes the pH of corrosion environment, and alters the reaction kinetics. The glass surface accumulates the corrosion products either in form of hydrated gel layers, which subsequently recrystallize (silica-based bioactive glasses) or directly recrystallizes into bone-like constituents, based on hydroxyapatite-like minerals (Ca₅(PO₄)₃OH) (HAp).

Bioactive properties of certain glass compositions have been proposed since Larry Hench discovered the signature 45S5 Bioglass^{©1}, proposing that ionic products of glass dissolution could increase healing rates inside the human body⁵. The main disadvantage of the 45S5 Bioglass[©] is its silica matrix. Although soluble to some extent, these glasses endure the corrosive environments for periods longer than 30 days^{6, 7}. The dissolution rate has been successfully reduced by adjusting the composition and the shape of the resulting material (e.g. fibers, microspheres⁸). Modified bioactive silicate glasses (13-93, 45S5) inevitably led to conclusions that not only silicate matrix, but also borate or phosphate glass networks produce hydroxyapatite-like material under corrosive conditions of simulated bodily environments⁹⁻¹¹.

This contribution proposes a novel bioactive glass composition, originating from a boron-containing alternatives to 45S5 Bioglass, specifically 13-93 glass. The new glass is characterised by its

BPS (boro-phospho-silicate) matrix. The contribution also summarises the results of its preliminary chemical analysis after melt-quenching synthesis and the process of optimization of the melting process in order to prepare the glass of desired composition.

In the early stages of experiments, two samples of boron-containing glass have been prepared: 13-93B1 borosilicate glass (34SiO₂ 19B₂O₃ 20CaO 12K₂O 5MgO 6Na₂O 4P₂O₅ wt%) and 13-93B3 borate glass (53B₂O₃ 20CaO 12K₂O 5MgO 6Na₂O 4P₂O₅ wt%). These boron-containing glasses were compared to the original Hench's silicate bioactive glass 45S5 (45SiO₂ 24.5CaO 24.5Na₂O 6P₂O₅ wt%). In the second run, two potentially bioactive glass compositions were calculated and subsequently synthesized by melt-quenching route, namely BPS1 (21B₂O₃ 11CaO 8K₂O 4MgO 5Na₂O 16P₂O₅ wt%) and BPS 2 (18B₂O₃ 20CaO 6K₂O 6MgO 6Na₂O 4P₂O₅ wt%). Conventional melt-quenching method (High-temperature furnace Classic 0718E) was utilized to melt the glasses at 1100°C, 1200°C and 1300°C (13-93B1, 13-93B3, BPS series, respectively.) Bulk glasses were pulverized and sieved to 25µm particle size fraction for further use.

Novel glass BPS 1 was proposed to be more similar to HAp in terms of Ca/P ratio, but the melting experiment proved that high P content leads to rapid crystallization of calcium and potassium phosphate from the glass melt, thus producing a borosilicate glass with crystalline phosphate phase, i.e. a glass-ceramic material.

The composition BPS 2 was prepared in glassy form, as verified by X-ray diffraction (Panalytical Empyrean, CuKα radiation, operated at 45 kV and 40 mA in the 2θ range 10 - 80°) TG and DSC (Netzsch STA 449 F1) analysis was used to determine the glass transition temperature, T_g, and melting point of all prepared glasses.

Density of the prepared glasses was determined by helium pycnometry (Quantachrome Ultrapyc 1200e). Determination of glass density is vital information for corrosion assays, with borosilicate glass densities resulting in 2.4 g cm⁻³.

Chemical analysis of listed materials was performed in cooperation with University of Technology, Brno, and Masaryk University, Brno. Quantification of elemental content was performed by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES Thermo iCap 6500 duo). With highly linear calibration (*i*² = 0.9999₉), accurate results were achieved in 3 sample runs for each sample (see below)

The future task is to perform static corrosion test in deionized water at 37 °C with subsequent analysis of the dissolution products, with following analysis of pH change during the dissolution and ICP analysis of the corrosion environment (deionised water)

Table 1 BPS glass ICP-OES analysis result summary

		SiO ₂	Na ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	CaO	B ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O
λ(nm)	λ(nm)	288.1	588.9	213.6	422.6	249.6	479.9
BPS1	wt%	35	5	14	11	21	6
	res.	35.2 ± 1.0	5.60 ± 0.19	16.14 ± 0.65	11.27 ± 0.48	20.36 ± 0.79	5.99 ± 0.39
BPS2	wt%	40	6	4	20	18	6
	res.	41.19 ± 0.65	6.45 ± 0.29	3.95 ± 0.14	20.49 ± 0.70	17.73 ± 0.70	6.10 ± 0.45

Keywords: bioactive glass, silicate glass, borate glass, ICP-OES, quantification, characterization, corrosion

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